

NONLINEAR ANALYSIS OF PROPAGATION OF DELAMINATION NEAR FREE EDGES

J.C.J. Schellekens and R. de Borst

Delft University of Technology, Department of Civil Engineering /

TNO Building and Construction Research

P.O. Box 5048, 2600 GA Delft, The Netherlands

ABSTRACT

Free edge delamination of a graphite-epoxy is simulated using nonlinear finite element analysis. Generalised plane strain elements and interface elements have been developed for this purpose. A mode-I crack model including strain softening is presented. Furthermore this contribution includes a formulation for strain-loading in nonlinear analysis which accounts for thermal and hygroscopic effects. In the nonlinear analyses delamination in $[+25_n/-25_n/90_n]_s$ laminates is examined. Results are in good agreement with experimental observations. In addition calculations show that the presented approach does not suffer from mesh dependency which implies that size effects can be described properly.

KEYWORDS: Delamination; Edge Effects; Failure Mechanism; Nonlinear Finite Element Analysis; Mode-I

1. INTRODUCTION

A failure mode often encountered in structural composite laminates is delamination, a phenomenon which has great influence on the structural integrity. In the last two decades many research activities have concentrated on the complex mechanisms of delamination. Due to the anisotropic material properties and the varying fibre orientations, each ply in the laminate tries to behave differently. Subsequently large edge stresses are necessary to preserve compatibility of the deformations. These large transverse normal and shear stresses are primarily responsible for the initiation of delamination. Analytical models have been developed for the treatment of free edge stress distributions (1,2,3). A historical review of these models is given by Pagano and Soni (4). Furthermore procedures to predict

delamination onset and growth based on the principle of virtual crack extension have been applied rather successfully by Crossman, Wang (5,6) and O'Brien (7) amongst others. Because of the mesh size dependency and stress singularities it is commonly believed that the use of stress based failure criteria does not produce relevant results as far as free edge delamination is concerned. However, Kim and Soni (8) indicated that an average stress approach combined with an anisotropic failure criterion results in an accurate prediction of the onset of delamination. The introduction of the ply thickness in the determination of stresses is essential in their approach.

In this contribution a nonlinear finite element procedure is developed for the prediction of delamination onset and growth. Although the failure criterion is based on stresses it is shown that, when combined with a softening type of post crack response, a stress based failure criterion results in a mesh objective calculation. The performance of the method is demonstrated by means of the analyses of free edge delamination in $[+25_n/-25_n/90_n]_s$ graphite-epoxy specimens under uniaxial tension.

In the examples twelve-noded cubic generalised plane strain elements with three translational degrees-of-freedom in each node have been used. These elements, which are assumed to remain elastic during the loading process, give an accurate representation of the stress concentrations near the free edges without the need for extreme mesh refinement. The individual plies are connected by cubic 3D line interface elements (9,10) which are well suited for modelling the geometric discontinuity that arises during delamination, which can either be gradual (softening type behaviour) or perfectly brittle. Also the effect of laminate thickness and the impact of thermal effects on the limit load has been studied.

2. GENERALISED PLANE-STRAIN ELEMENTS

In free edge delamination testing specimens are subjected to a uniaxial load. It is assumed that at a certain distance from the ends of the specimen the in-plane displacements are independent of the x-coordinate (see Figure 1).

FIGURE 1. Geometry of the specimen.

This allows us to introduce for the displacement field of a cross-section (1,3,7),

$$\begin{aligned} u_x(x,y,z) &= \epsilon_x x + u_x(y,z) \\ u_y(x,y,z) &= u_y(y,z) \\ u_z(x,y,z) &= u_z(y,z) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

with ϵ_x the strain that is prescribed in the x-direction of the specimen. If we define a matrix \mathbf{H} which contains the interpolation polynomials, so that $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{a}$, and a differential operator \mathbf{L}

$$\mathbf{L}^T = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

we obtain

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{a} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_1 \quad (3)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_1 = (\epsilon_x, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$ denotes the externally applied strain vector and $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{LH}$ is the strain displacement matrix. If we introduce ΔT and ΔC denoting the changes in temperature and moisture content and vectors $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ and $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ containing the thermal and hygroscopic expansion coefficients respectively, the expression for the strain vector becomes

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \mathbf{B}\Delta\mathbf{a} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_1 - \Delta T\boldsymbol{\alpha} - \Delta C\boldsymbol{\gamma}. \quad (4)$$

In a nonlinear analysis the total load is applied in an incremental fashion and within each loading step equilibrium is achieved in an iterative manner, which is different from linear elastic analyses. For the incremental strains $\Delta\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_j$ in a nonlinear analysis we can write

$$\Delta\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_j = \mathbf{B}\Delta\mathbf{a}_j + \Delta\lambda_j\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_1 - \Delta T_i\boldsymbol{\alpha} - \Delta C_i\boldsymbol{\gamma} \quad (5)$$

where j denotes the iteration number, $\Delta\lambda_j$ is the value of the incremental load parameter in the current iteration and ΔT_i and ΔC_i are the incremental changes in temperature and moisture content in loading step i . The incremental nodal displacement vector is given by $\Delta\mathbf{a}_j$. Furthermore in a nonlinear analysis the material constants in $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ and $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ can be functions of the temperature and moisture content respectively. From eq. (5) it follows with the elastic stress-strain matrix for the plies \mathbf{D} that the incremental stresses are given by

$$\Delta\boldsymbol{\sigma}_j = \mathbf{D} \left(\mathbf{B}\Delta\mathbf{a}_j + \Delta\lambda_j\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_1 - \Delta T_i\boldsymbol{\alpha} - \Delta C_i\boldsymbol{\gamma} \right) \quad (6)$$

If $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{i-1}$ represents the total stress vector at the end of step $i-1$ the total stress at the end of iteration j

reads

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_j = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{i-1} + \mathbf{D} \left(\mathbf{B} \Delta \mathbf{a}_j + \Delta \lambda_j \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1 - \Delta T_i \boldsymbol{\alpha} - \Delta C_i \boldsymbol{\gamma} \right) \quad (7)$$

The expressions for the internal and external force vectors for strain loading then read

$$\mathbf{f}_j = \int_V \mathbf{B}^T (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_j - \lambda_j \mathbf{D} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1) dV \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{f}_e = -\lambda_0 \int_V \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1 dV \quad (8)$$

where λ_0 is the total load factor at the beginning of the current step. Denoting the structural stiffness matrix by \mathbf{K} the incremental displacements can be solved iteratively from

$$\mathbf{K} \Delta \mathbf{a}_j = \mathbf{f}_e - \mathbf{f}_{j-1}. \quad (9)$$

3. FORMULATION OF INTERFACE ELEMENTS AND DISCRETE CRACKING

FIGURE 2. Cubic line interface element.

The individual plies in the laminate are connected by interface elements (see Figure 2). These elements have the ability to model the geometrical discontinuity which is introduced by delamination. In the elastic stage of the calculation no additional deformations are allowed in the finite element model because of these interface elements. Therefore a sufficiently high dummy stiffness has to be supplied. In contrast to continuum elements interface elements do not keep track of stresses and strains at the integration points, but consider tractions and relative displacements. With the differential operator matrix \mathbf{L} and the interpolation matrix \mathbf{H} defined as

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & +1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & +1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & +1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{n} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{n} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mathbf{n} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathbf{n} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathbf{n} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathbf{n} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

with \mathbf{n} the interpolation polynomial vector and the nodal displacement vector

$$\mathbf{a} = (u_z^1, u_z^2, \dots, u_z^n, u_y^1, u_y^2, \dots, u_y^n, u_x^1, u_x^2, \dots, u_x^n), \quad (11)$$

the relative displacements are related to the nodal displacements through

$$\Delta \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{L} \mathbf{H} \mathbf{a}. \quad (12)$$

If we denote \mathbf{D} as the tangent stiffness relation the tractions $\mathbf{t} = (t_z, t_y, t_x)$ are obtained from

$$\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{D} \Delta \mathbf{u}. \quad (13)$$

For a line interface element in a generalised plane strain situation the element stiffness matrix is derived as

$$\mathbf{K} = \int_{\xi=-1}^{\xi=+1} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi} d\xi. \quad (14)$$

Once the elastic limit in an integration point of the interface element is exceeded the traction-relative displacement relation \mathbf{D} becomes nonlinear and is determined by a discrete crack model. In the present model crack initiation is supposed to be purely in mode-I. A crack arises when the traction t_z normal the plies exceeds the tensile strength f_t . It is recognised that a stress criterion cannot predict onset of the delamination correctly. Depending on the type of material the traction and stiffness in a mode-I crack may abruptly or gradually reduce to zero. The first phenomenon is called brittle failure, whereas the gradual decrease of the crack traction and stiffness with increasing relative displacements is called softening behaviour. The use of a softening type of response results in a rate controlled delamination.

For the derivation of the nonlinear stiffness relation we will use a decomposed approach (9,10) in which the total relative displacement consists of an elastic part $\Delta \mathbf{u}^{el}$ and an inelastic part which is equal to the crack relative displacement $\Delta \mathbf{u}^{cr}$. In the crack model the incremental tractions $\Delta \mathbf{t}$ for the intact material are given by

$$\Delta \mathbf{t} = \mathbf{D} \Delta \Delta \mathbf{u}^{el}. \quad (15)$$

Herein $\Delta \Delta \mathbf{u}^{el}$ is the incremental elastic relative displacement vector. The incremental crack-relative displacements $\Delta \Delta \mathbf{u}^{cr}$ are related to the incremental tractions according to

$$\Delta \mathbf{t} = \mathbf{D}^{cr} \Delta \Delta \mathbf{u}^{cr} \quad (16)$$

where \mathbf{D}^{cr} is the crack stiffness matrix which is dependent on the mode-I post crack relation. The total incremental relative displacement is written as

$$\Delta \Delta \mathbf{u} = \Delta \Delta \mathbf{u}^{el} + \Delta \Delta \mathbf{u}^{cr}. \quad (17)$$

Substituting eqs. (15) and (16) in eq. (17) results in

$$\Delta t = \left[\mathbf{D}^{-1} + (\mathbf{D}^{cr})^{-1} \right]^{-1} \Delta \Delta \mathbf{u}, \quad (18)$$

or using the Sherman-Morrison-Woodbury formula

$$\Delta t = \left[\mathbf{D} - \mathbf{D} \left[\mathbf{D}^{cr} + \mathbf{D} \right]^{-1} \mathbf{D} \right] \Delta \Delta \mathbf{u}. \quad (19)$$

This relation reduces to zero for brittle failure.

4. DELAMINATION IN $[\pm 25_n / -25_n / 90_n]_s$ GRAPHITE EPOXY LAMINATES

For the investigation of the mesh-dependency of delamination growth a 6-ply $[\pm 25/90]_s$ graphite epoxy laminate (see Table 1 for material properties) was subjected to a uniaxial strain load (6). Residual curing stresses due to a temperature drop of $\Delta T = -125^\circ\text{C}$ were taken into account. Hygroscopic effects were not included in the analyses. Since delamination is initiated at the 90/90 ply interface a pure mode-I crack extension results. The dimensions of the cross section of the laminate are 25.0 \times 0.792 mm with a ply-thickness equal to 0.132 mm.

TABLE 1. Material properties for As-3501-06 Graphite Epoxy [MPa]

Young's Moduli		Shear Moduli		Poisson Ratios		Thermal Exp. Coeff.	
E_{11}	$140 \cdot 10^{+3}$	G_{12}	$5.5 \cdot 10^{+3}$	ν_{12}	0.29	α_{11}	$0.36 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$
E_{22}	$11 \cdot 10^{+3}$	G_{13}	$5.5 \cdot 10^{+3}$	ν_{13}	0.29	α_{22}	$28.8 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$
E_{33}	$11 \cdot 10^{+3}$	G_{23}	$5.5 \cdot 10^{+3}$	ν_{23}	0.29	α_{33}	$28.8 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$

Due to the symmetry of the laminate only a quarter of the cross-section was modelled (see Figure 3) using cubic generalised plane strain elements. Translations in the z-direction along the y-axis and translations in the x- and y-directions along the z-axis were prevented.

FIGURE 3. Finite element mesh

Cubic line interface elements were supplied between the 90 degrees plies. A 4×4 Gauß integration scheme was used for generalised plane strain elements. For the interface elements a nodal lumping scheme was applied since Gaußian integration leads to oscillatory traction profiles (10). For the dummy stiffness of the interface elements a value of 10^{+8}N/mm^3 was substituted, the tensile strength was chosen equal to $f_t = 51.6 \text{ N/mm}^2$. A linear softening relation determines the post crack response in the interface elements.

Mesh-objectivity was examined using three different meshes with a varying number of elements over the width of the specimen. In all cases the element height was chosen equal to the ply thickness. The part of the specimen within 5 mm of the free edge was modelled using 50, 100 and 200 elements respectively for each ply (element lengths: 0.1, 0.05 and 0.025 mm). The remaining 7.5 mm was modelled using three elements per ply. To achieve a rate controlled delamination a fracture energy $G_f = 0.175 \text{ N/mm}$ was supplied. The nonlinear analyses starts with a stepwise decrease of the temperature to -125°C followed by the application of the uniaxial strain load. Figure 4 shows the results for the three different meshes.

FIGURE 4. Mesh-objectivity

Left: Axial load versus applied uniaxial strain

Right: Applied uniaxial strain versus delamination length

The obtained value for the ultimate uniaxial strain $\epsilon_u = 0.53\%$ is in good agreement with the result $\epsilon_u = 0.57\%$ that can be derived from data of References (6) and (11). In addition it is observed that, upon

mesh refinement, the different analyses converge to the same solution. Hence, results are not influenced by the different element sizes. It is mentioned that the snap back in the left diagram was triggered using an indirect displacement control in which the crack opening displacement is used as a constraint for the determination of the load parameter $\Delta\lambda$. For a description of this procedure the reader is referred to Ref. (12). A deformed geometry of the mesh with 100 elements per ply for a delamination of 4.37 mm is presented in Figure 5. The scale of deformation is 1.0.

FIGURE 5. Deformed laminate at a delamination length of 4.37 mm.

To investigate the effect of the value of the tensile strength on the ultimate tensile strain two additional analyses were performed in which f_t was varied between 90% and 110% of the original value (46.44 N/mm² and 56.76 N/mm²). The results which are shown in Figure 6 show a maximum shift of 2.0% in the values for the ultimate uniaxial strain.

FIGURE 6. Influence of 10% variation in tensile strength
 Left: Axial load versus applied uniaxial strain
 Right: Applied uniaxial strain versus delamination length

Analyses on $[+25_n/-25_n/90_n]_s$ ($n=1,2,3$) laminates were performed to assess the capability of our approach to deal with size-effects. In the analyses a fracture energy G_f equal to 0.175 N/mm and an element length of 0.05 mm were used. Three different loading paths were followed in order to investigate the path dependency of the laminate response. In the first case (I) the temperature loading is followed by the strain loading. Secondly the laminates were analysed by first imposing strain loading and then temperature loading (II). In a third series of analyses both load cases were applied simultaneously (III). Figure 7 illustrates the effect of the laminate thickness on the laminate response.

FIGURE 7. Ultimate strains for $[+25_n/-25_n/90_n]_s$ ($n = 1,2,3$) laminates

For cases II and III it is observed that the ultimate strain depends inversely on the square root of the laminate thickness, as indicated by the dashed line. Crossman, Wang (5,6) and O'Brien (7) reported the same dependency. However, when temperature loading is followed by the strain loading the results for the $n=2$ and $n=3$ laminates do not follow this pattern, which would suggest an influence of the loading path on the ultimate strain.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

A fully nonlinear finite element approach which accounts for thermal and hygroscopic effects has been proposed for the analysis of free edge delamination problems in composite laminates. Although a stress criterion is used for the initiation of delamination no influence of mesh-refinement on the ultimate strength of the laminates is encountered. This is a result of the softening type of response after cracking. The obtained value for the ultimate strain for the $[\pm 25/90]_s$ laminates corresponds with the

value obtained in References (6) and (11). It has been demonstrated that in the present approach the ultimate uniaxial strain is rather insensitive to changes in value of the tensile strength f_t . It is believed that the present method results in a proper treatment of size effects, although a proper explanation does not yet exist for the discrepancy in the results for the 12 and 18 ply laminates in the case that temperature loading precedes strain loading. Preliminary calculations at least suggest that the material shows a path dependent behaviour. This would cast some doubt on the applicability of linear elastic fracture mechanics in the prediction of delamination onset and growth.

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J.C.J. Schellekens

Han Schellekens, born in 1964, earned his Ir. degree in Civil Engineering in 1988 from the Delft University of Technology. He is currently working on his Phd. thesis which concentrates on the finite element modelling of composite materials.

R. de Borst

René de Borst, born in 1958, earned his Ir. degree in Civil Engineering in 1982 and his Dr. degree in 1986, both from the Delft University of Technology. He has been a member of the DIANA group of TNO Building and Construction Research since 1982. Since 1988 he is professor in Civil Engineering at the Delft University of Technology.

